

GASTRORETENSIVE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM: AN REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

English oral delivery of drug was the commonly used modality because of patient compliance and ease of administration. After oral administration of any drug, its bioavailability is affected by its residence time in stomach. Recently, gastro retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) have gained wide acceptance for drugs with a narrow absorption window, decreased stability at high alkaline pH, and increased solubility at low pH. This approach develops a drug delivery system, which gets retained within gastric fluid, thereby releasing its active principles in the stomach. Some methods used to achieve gastric retention of drugs include the use of effervescence agents, mucoadhesive polymers, magnetic material, bouncy enhancing excipient, and techniques that form plug-like devices that resist gastric emptying. This review provides a concise account of various attributes of recently developed approaches for GRDDS.

KEYWORDS: Gastro retentive, Bioavailability, bio/mucoadhesive system, therapeutic window, gastric emptying, GRDDS.

INTRODUCTION

Gastro-retentive drug delivery systems (GRDDS) represent a novel approach in drug administration. Their primary objective is to prolong the residence time of a medication in the stomach, ensuring site-specific release in the upper gastrointestinal tract for both local and systemic effects. The gastric retention time (GRT) of formulations designed for gastro-retentive administration is significantly enhanced by their extended stomach residence. Over the past few decades, a variety of techniques for gastro-retentive drug administration have been developed. Oral delivery remains the most practical and recommended method for achieving systemic circulation of medications.^[1] Recently, the pharmaceutical industry has shown increasing interest in oral controlled-release drug delivery systems due to their potential to improve therapeutic outcomes. Advantages include simplified dosing, increased patient compliance, and formulation flexibility.

Medications with short half-lives and rapid gastrointestinal absorption are quickly eliminated from the body, necessitating frequent dosing to maintain therapeutic levels. To address this issue, oral sustained-release formulations have been developed that gradually release drugs into the gastrointestinal tract, thereby maintaining stable effective drug concentrations in systemic circulation for an extended period. These delivery systems are engineered to remain in the stomach after oral administration, releasing the drug in a controlled manner that provides a continuous supply to the gastro intestinal tract (GIT) absorption sites. However, short GRT and irregular gastric emptying time (GET) present challenges, as they can lead to partial drug release in the absorption zone (the stomach or upper small intestine) and reduced dosage efficacy. Prolonged stomach residence is optimal for enhancing site-specific controlled-release formulations, as it can improve drug solubility, reduce drug wastage, extend the release duration, and enhance the bioavailability of drugs that are poorly soluble in high pH conditions. Additionally, extended gastric retention may benefit local treatments in the upper small intestine, such as peptic ulcer therapy.

OBJECTIVE

The present study attempts to give an insight into the gastro retentive drug delivery systems, and gastric floating tablets, in particular. These have attracted the interest of many formulators due to their advantages over the conventional drug delivery systems, recently.

The study highlights these advantages with reference to the various types of gastro retentive drug delivery systems, as well as provides an overview of the recent advances that have taken place in this area.

Anatomy and physiology of the stomach

Knowledge about the anatomy and physiology of the stomach is essential for the successful formulation of gastro retentive dosage forms. Anatomically, the stomach is divided into three areas: the proximal portion toward the oesophagus is fundus, followed by the body, which serves as a storage site for engulfed food, and the antrum, last part that connects the body to the small intestine. Antrum helps in churning action and in gastric emptying. In fasting state, a sequence of contractions occurs cyclically through the stomach and intestine every 120-180 min, called the migrating myoelectric cycle. It is further divided into four phases. The pattern of contraction changes in a fed state is termed as the digestive motility pattern.^[2]

Fig 1: Motility pattern in gastro intestinal tract.

Anatomically the stomach is divided into three regions: Fundus, body and antrum (pylorus). The proximal part made of fundus and body act as reservoir for undigested materials, whereas the antrum is the main site for mixing motions and act as pump from gastric emptying by propelling the actions. Gastric emptying occurs during fasting as well as feed state.^[3] The pattern of motility is however distinct in 2 states. During fasting state an inter digestive series of electrical events takes place, which cycle both through stomach and intestine every 2 to 3 hours. This is called the inter digestive myoelectric cycle or migrating myoelectric cycle (MMC), which is further divided into following 4 phases as described by Wilson and Washington.

1. Phase I (basal phase) lasts from 40 to 60 minutes with contractions.
2. Phase II (pre burst phase) lasts for 40 to 60 minutes with intermittent action potential and contractions. As the phase progress the intensity and frequency also increase gradually.
3. Phase III (burst phase) last for 4 to 6 minutes. It includes intense and regular contractions for short period. It is due to this valve that all the un digested material is swept out of the stomach down to the small intestine .it is also known as the house keeper wave.
4. Phase IV last for 0 to 5 minutes and occurs between phases III and I of 2 consecutive cycles.

After the ingestion of a mixed meal, the pattern of contractions changes from fasted to that of fed state. This is also known as digestive motility pattern and comprises continuous contractions as in phase II of fasted state. These contractions result in reducing the size of food particles (to less than 1mm) which are propelled toward the pylorus in a suspension form. During the fed state onset of MMC is delayed resulting in slowdown of gastric emptying rate. Scintigraphy studies determining gastric emptying rates revealed that orally administered controlled release dosage form are subjected to basically two complications that of short gastric residence time and unpredictable gastric emptying rate.

Fig 2: Anatomical structure of stomach.

Physicochemical properties of GRDDS

Physicochemical properties of GRDDS include density, size, and shape of the dosage form, which play major roles in the formulation of GRDDS. The dosage forms having a density lower than the gastric contents can float to the surface, while high-density systems sink to the bottom of the stomach.^[4] For an ideal formulation, the density should be in the range of 1.0-2.5 g/cm³. Dosage forms having a diameter of more than 7.5 mm show better gastric residence time (GRT). Circular, spherical or tetrahedron-shaped devices show excellent gastro retentive properties.

Physiological factors affecting retention of GRDDS in the stomach

The most important factors controlling the gastric retention time of dosage forms include fed or unfed state, nature of the meal, caloric content, and frequency of feeding. In the case of a fasting environment, gastric retention time is less due to the increase in GI motility. Emptying of gastric content occurs due to peristalsis. If peristalsis coincides with dosage form administration, the gastric residence is short. However, after meals, peristalsis is delayed and may help increase the gastric residence of the formulation. A high-calorie meal containing proteins, fats, and fibrous compounds increases gastric retention time.^[5] In the case of multiple meals, the gastric retention is more than a single meal due to persistent inhibition of peristalsis.

Also, some other factors, such as sex and age, affect gastric retention. Compared with males, females have a slower gastric emptying time irrespective of height, weight, and body surface. A person at the age of more than 70 exhibits longer GRT. In comparison, neonates show less GRT compared with geriatric patients.

Gastro retentive dosage form approaches

Continuous research and advancements in various approaches to gastroretentive dosage forms over the last few years are as presented in figure 3. These approaches to GRDDS help in delivering the medicament in a sustained and restrained way through the gastrointestinal tract.

Fig 3: Approaches of gastro retentive drug delivery system.

The function of GRDDS in treating *Helicobacter pylori*:

By extending the residence time of medications in the stomach, GRDDS enhance the bioavailability and efficacy of therapies targeting *H. pylori*. The following GRDDS approaches are employed.

Floating systems

These systems, which include floating tablets and beads, use low-density polymers to remain buoyant in the stomach for extended periods.^[6]

Mucoadhesive systems

These systems adhere to the stomach mucosa to provide long-lasting local medication administration.

Swelling and expanding systems

These systems expand upon contact with gastric fluids to prevent premature emptying.

High-density systems

These systems sink to the bottom of the stomach and remain there longer.

Magnetic systems

These systems use external magnets to maintain the drug formulation within the stomach. The contribution of GRDDS to the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*.

GRDDS enhance medication absorption, prolong the residence time of drugs in the stomach, and improve patient compliance through reduced dosing frequency.^[7] These benefits help lower the risk of antibiotic resistance associated with prolonged antibiotic use.

ADVANTAGES

GRDDS offer several advantages. Namely, these systems:

- Optimize dose utilization in a cost-effective manner.
- Minimize the risk of antibiotic resistance by maintaining constant therapeutic levels.
- Improve drug release efficiency, especially for medications with short half-lives.
- Favourably influence pharmacokinetic characteristics
- Promote patient compliance by reducing dosing frequency
- Remain buoyant in the stomach due to the lower bulk density of gastric fluid, thereby mitigating issues related to GET and GRT.

DISADVANTAGES

GRDDS have several drawbacks.

- Some drugs exhibit limited solubility in acidic environments, and first-pass metabolism may pose challenges.
- Drugs that cause gastrointestinal irritation, are unstable in acidic conditions, have low solubility in gastric fluids, or are intended for targeted release in the colon are not suitable for GRDDS.
- The performance of GRDDS can vary depending on whether they are administered before or after a meal, as gastric residence time is influenced by the individual's digestive state. It is challenging to predict drug adherence due to the continuous renewal of the stomach's mucus layer.

Approaches to gastric retention

The retention of an oral dosage form in the stomach, for example, bio adhesive approach in which the adhesive capacity of some polymer with glycoprotein is closely applied to the epithelial surface of stomach.^[8] Other approaches include: high density and low-density approach. Fig.4.

1) High density approach

For preparing such type of formulations, the density of the pellets should be higher than the stomach fluid. It would be at least 1.50 g/ml. In this type, the drug can be coated or mixed with heavy, nontoxic materials such as barium sulphate, titanium dioxide, etc.

2) Low density approach

Floating systems come under low density approach. In this approach, the density of pellets should be less than 1 g/ml, so as to float the pellets or tablets in the gastric fluid and, release the drug slowly for a longer period of time. This type is also called as Hydrodynamically Balanced System (HBS).

Fig 4: Diagrammatic representation of high density and low-density approaches.

3. Floating Drug Delivery systems and its mechanism

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) have bulk density lesser than gastric fluids, so they remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time.^[9] While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system as shown in fig.6 However, besides a minimal gastric content needed to allow the proper achievement of the buoyancy retention principle, a minimal level of floating force (F) is also required to keep the dosage form reliably buoyant on the surface of the meal. To measure the floating force kinetics, a novel apparatus for determination of resultant weight has been reported in the literature. This apparatus helps in optimizing FDDS with respect to stability and durability of floating forces produced in order to prevent the drawbacks of unforeseeable intragastric buoyancy capability variations¹⁶.

$$F = F \text{ buoyancy} - F \text{ gravity} = (D_f - D_s) g v$$

Where,

F= total vertical force,

D_f = fluid density,

D_s= object density,

v = volume and

g = acceleration due to gravity.

Fig 5: mechanism of floating drug delivery system.

Classification of floating system

1). Single Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Effervescent system

b) Non-effervescent Systems

2). Multiple Unit Floating Dosage Systems

- a) Effervescent Systems
 - b) Non-effervescent Systems
 - c) Hollow microspheres
- ## 3). Raft forming system

1). Single Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Effervescent systems

Effervescent floating drug delivery systems generate gas (CO₂), thus reduce the density of the system, and remain buoyant in the stomach for a prolonged period of time and release the drug slowly at a desired rate. The main ingredients of effervescent system include swellable polymers like chitosan, methyl cellulose and effervescent compounds such as citric acid, sodium bicarbonate, citric acid and tartaric acid. Penners et al prepared Available online at www.ijpras.com 6 an expandable tablet containing mixture of polyvinyl lactams and polyacrylates that swells rapidly in an aqueous environment and thus, stays in stomach over an extended period of time. In addition to this, gas-forming agents were also incorporated so as soon as the gas formed, the density of the system was reduced and thus, the system tended to float in the gastric environment. prepared the effervescent floating tablet of famotidine.^[10] They found that the addition of gel forming polymers methocel (K100 and K15M) and gas-generating agent sodium bicarbonate along with citric acid was essential to achieve in vitro buoyancy. The drug release from the tablets was sufficiently sustained and non-Fiskian transport of the drug from tablets was confirmed.

b) Non effervescent system

Non-effervescent systems commonly use gel forming or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, polysaccharides and matrix forming polymers such as polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate, and polystyrene. The formulation method includes a simple approach of thoroughly mixing the drug and the gel-forming hydrocolloid. After oral administration, this dosage form swells in contact with gastric fluids and attains a bulk density of less than 1g/ml. The air entrapped within the swollen matrix imparts buoyancy to the dosage form. Iann Uccelli et al prepared air compartment multiple unit system for prolonged gastric residence. These units were composed of a calcium alginate core separated by an air compartment from membrane of calcium alginate. The porous structure generated by leaching of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), which was employed as water soluble additive in

coating composition, was found to increase the membrane permeability preventing the air compartment shrinkage. The ability of floatation increases with increase in PVA, molecular Weight²⁰. Wu et al prepared floating sustained release tablets of nimodipine by using HPMC and PEG 6000. Prior to formulation of floating tablets, nimodipine was incorporated into poloxamer-188 solid dispersion after which it was directly compressed into floating tablets.

It was observed that by increasing the HPMC and decreasing the PEG 6000 content, a decline in in vitro release of nimodipine occurred. ²¹ Single unit formulations are associated with problems such as sticking together or being obstructed in the gastrointestinal tract, which may have a potential danger of producing irritation.^[11] The main drawback of such system is “all or none” phenomenon. In such cases, there is a danger of passing of the dosage form to intestinal part at the time of house-keeper waves. To overcome this difficulty multiple, unit dosage forms are designed.

Effervescent multiple unit systems, as compared to the effervescent systems. However, few workers have reported the possibility of developing such system containing indomethacin, using chitosan as the polymeric excipient. A multiple unit HBS containing indomethacin as a model drug prepared by extrusion process is reported (Tardi and Troy, 2002). A mixture of drug, chitosan and acetic acid is extruded through a needle, and the extrudate is cut and dried. Chitosan hydrates and floats in the acidic media, and the required drug release could be obtained by modifying the drug-polymer ratio.^[12]

Fig 6: (a) Different layers semi permeable membrane, effervescent layer, core pill layer, (b) mechanism of floatation via co2 liberation.

The effect of formulation variables on in vitro performance of floating sustained release of verapamil. The formulations were comprised of variables like polymers excipients, polymer content, density of capsule and amount of effervescent Agents ²².

2). Multiple Unit Floating Systems

Multiple unit dosage forms may be an attractive alternate since they have been shown to reduce inter and intra-subject variabilities in drug absorption as well as to lower the possibility of dose dumping.^[13] Various multiple unit floating systems have been developed in Available online at www.ijpras.com 7 different forms, and using principles such as air compartment multiple unit system, hollow microspheres prepared by emulsion solvent diffusion method, beads prepared by emulsion gelation method. Use of effervescent and swellable polymer is another approach for preparing multiple unit FDDS.

a) Effervescent system

Ichikawa et al developed a new multiple type of floating dosage system composed of effervescent layers and swellable membrane layers coated on sustained release pills. The inner layer of effervescent agents containing sodium bicarbonate and tartaric acid was divided into two sublayers to avoid direct contact between the two agents. These sublayers were surrounded by a swellable polymer membrane containing polyvinyl acetate and purified shellac. When this system was immersed in the buffer at 37°C, it settled down and the solution permeated into the effervescent layer through the outer swellable membrane. CO₂ was generated by the neutralization reaction between the two effervescent agents, producing swollen pills (like balloons) with a density less than 1.0 g/ml Polycarbonate in dichloromethane was found to give hollow microspheres that floated on water and simulated biofluids, as evidenced by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).^[14]

High drug loading was achieved and drug-loaded microspheres were able to float on gastric and intestinal fluids. It was found that increasing the drug to polymer ratio increased both their mean particle size and release rate of drug 24. Sheth et al. developed hydrodynamically balanced capsules containing mixture of drug and hydrocolloids containing a homogeneous mixture of drug and the hydrocolloid in a capsule, which upon contact with gastric fluid acquired and maintained a bulk density of less than 1, thereby being buoyant on the gastric contents of stomach, until all the drug was released as shown in fig.7.

Fig 7: working principle of hydro dynamically balanced system.

b) Hollow microspheres

Both natural and synthetic polymers have been used to prepare floating microspheres. Joseph *et al.* developed a floating dosage form of piroxicam based on hollow polycarbonate microspheres. The microspheres were prepared by the solvent evaporation technique. Encapsulation efficiency of ~95% was achieved. *In vivo* studies were performed in healthy male albino rabbits. Pharmacokinetic analysis was derived from plasma concentration versus time plot and revealed that the bioavailability from the piroxicam microspheres alone was 1.4 times that of the free drug and 4.8 times that of a dosage form consisting of microspheres plus the loading dose and was capable of sustained delivery of the drug over a prolonged period.^[15]

3) Raft forming system

Raft forming systems have received much attention for the drug delivery for gastrointestinal infections and disorders. The mechanism involved in the raft formation includes the formation of viscous cohesive gel in contact with gastric fluids, wherein each portion of the liquid swells forming a continuous layer called a raft. This raft floats on gastric fluids because of low bulk density created by the formation of CO₂. Usually, the system ingredients include a gel forming agent and alkaline bicarbonates or carbonates responsible for the formation of CO₂ to make the system less dense and float on the gastric fluids. Jorgen *et al* described an

antacid raft forming floating system. The system contains a gel forming agent (e.g. sodium alginate), sodium bicarbonate and acid neutralizer, which forms a foaming sodium alginate gel (raft), which when comes in contact with gastric fluids, the raft floats on the gastric fluids and prevents the reflux of the gastric contents (i.e. gastric acid) into the oesophagus by acting as a barrier between the stomach and oesophagus.

Applications of GRDDS

Site-specific drug delivery systems

These systems are particularly beneficial for drugs that are selectively absorbed from the stomach or the proximal small intestine.^[16] Controlled, slow delivery of the drug to the stomach minimizes systemic exposure while providing sufficient local therapeutic doses, thereby reducing adverse effects on blood flow. Additionally, prolonged gastric availability through site-directed delivery may decrease dosing frequency. For example, this approach has been applied with furosemide and riboflavin.

Enhanced bioavailability

The bioavailability of non-controlled-release polymeric formulations can be significantly improved by using riboflavin-controlled release gastro-retentive dosage forms. Drug absorption is influenced by multiple factors within the gastrointestinal tract that affect both absorption and transit.

Sustained drug delivery

The short GRT of conventional oral controlled-release formulations can be overcome by HBS systems, which—due to their low bulk density—float over the gastrointestinal contents and remain in the stomach for extended periods. Their large size prevents passage through the pyloric opening.^[17]

Minimized adverse activity at the colon

By retaining the medication in the stomach, HBS systems reduce the amount of drug that reaches the colon, thereby minimizing undesirable effects. This is particularly important for beta-lactam antibiotics, which are absorbed primarily in the small intestine; their presence in the colon can promote microbial resistance.

Absorption enhancement

Drugs with limited bioavailability due to site-specific absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract may be ideal candidates for floating drug delivery system formulations, which maximize absorption.

Reduced fluctuations in drug concentration

Following GRDDS administration, blood drug levels remain within a narrower range compared to immediate-release formulations. This consistent delivery minimizes fluctuations in pharmacological action and may help prevent concentration-dependent adverse effects associated with peak concentrations.

Challenges ahead with GRDDS

The retention time of the dosage forms in the GIT is one of the determinants of the bioavailability of oral drug delivery systems. In case of GRDDS, it is rather specific to the stomach only. Therefore, for developing a GRDDS, the main challenge is retaining the delivery system in the stomach or the upper part of the small intestine for a long time until all the drugs have been released at a predetermined rate. The process of gastric emptying time is highly variable. Among many other factors, it mainly depends on the dosage form as well as fed or fasted state of the stomach.^[18] The gastric retention time is extended in the fed state, whereas shortened by the fasting state. Other physiological barriers and factors like the type of food, caloric content, gender and age play significant roles in the variation of gastric emptying time. Because of high caloric content, high fat meal strongly prolongs the process of gastric emptying. Indigestible polymers or fatty acid salts also modify the motility pattern of the stomach under fed state and help in reducing gastric emptying rate. Additionally, patients have variable GRT depending on gender and age, as reported by Mojaverian et al. The pylorus limitation plays an important role in gastric retention of any GRDDS. The pylorus size is about 2 to 3 mm during the digestion and the diameter becomes 12.8 ± 7.0 mm during the inter-digestive phase.^[19] Thus, all particles must have a diameter lower than 5 mm so that they can pass through the pylorus into the duodenum. Another factor to consider here is the variation in pylorus size and its peristaltic movement of the animal (e.g. dog, rabbit model) from that of the human. So, *in vivo* efficacy results need to be concluded carefully. Size and shape of the dosage form, individual's disease state, and body mass index are some other factors on which gastric residence time is dependent and related to the efficacy of the dosage form. However, it has been reported that sometimes multiple-unit GRDDS shows an

improved and predictable drug release compared to a single-unit GRDDS. Due to a combination of the lag time and the gastric emptying process, a single unit gastro-retentive dosage form (GRDF) may ultimately exit the stomach before the dosage form becomes functional.^[20] Hence, to develop an optimum GRDDS, the main challenges are to overcome the problems associated with the gastric emptying rate of the stomach together with maintaining an appropriate drug release rate for an extended period of time before it gets metabolized in the system.

CONCLUSION

As our understanding of gastrointestinal physiology and its impact on drug delivery deepens, more advanced drug delivery systems will be developed to optimize the administration of substances with region-specific absorption. Advances in delivery technologies will lead to the creation of more gastro-retentive drug administration techniques, particularly for drugs with extended half-lives, limited bioavailability, or significant first-pass metabolism. A review of the literature indicates that, because the upper gastrointestinal tract is the primary site for drug absorption, gastro-retentive drug delivery maximizes absorption and enhances absolute bioavailability, offering several advantages for drugs with low bioavailability. This strategy not only maximizes patient benefit but also improves patient compliance. Given the increasing efficacy of various pharmacotherapies, it is likely that GRDDS technologies will be more frequently utilized in the future for systemic drug delivery.

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